

The Deep Learning Frontier in Deepfake Detection: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract

The advancement of deep learning and generative artificial intelligence has significantly the positive and negative aspects of multimedia content in social networking communities. Recently, numerous complaints have been filed worldwide regarding deepfake videos. These shared deepfake videos have degraded the trust of individuals and communities. Deepfake video detection is a major challenge due to the high similarity index between deepfake and real videos. Deepfake detection techniques mostly target video media covering manipulations like DeepFakes, Face2Face, and FaceSwap with limited exploration of still images. Approaches that incorporate data augmentation or self-blended image generation tend to improve cross-domain performance, yet several methods experience significant degradation when tested on low-resolution or mixed-manipulation synthetic media. The objective of this paper is to provide the researcher a better understanding of how deepfakes are generated and identified, the latest developments and breakthroughs in this realm, weaknesses of existing security methods, and focus on areas requiring more investigation. Reviewed research paper results mostly based on deepfake detection methods using convolutional neural networks, EfficientNet, and hybrid architectures consistently achieve in-library accuracies between 90% and 100% on benchmark datasets such as FaceForensics++ and CelebDF. In contrast, cross-library evaluations reveal performance drops: some methods maintain accuracies above 90%, while others decline into a 50% to 90% rang for example, one method reported an in-library AUC of 97.2% that fell to 57.2% across libraries. Only a few studies specify computational costs; one reports inference times exceeding 5 ms per frame on an NVIDIA 2080Ti GPU with 128 GB RAM.

Keywords: Deepfake, Video, Deep Learning, CNN, EfficientNet

Introduction

The advancement of digital technology and communication systems has significantly increased the data capacity of social networking communities, including platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and many others. This technological growth has empowered users to create and share digital content, such as videos, audio, and images, as recorded multimedia data[1]. However, alongside this positive trend, there is a concerning rise in the creation and dissemination of fake and manipulated multimedia content, often referred to as deepfakes. Deepfakes, which are created using advanced deep learning and generative artificial intelligence technologies[2,3], manipulate videos and images in ways that can be highly convincing. These fake videos and images can defame individuals, groups, or communities, and contribute to the spread of hate and misinformation in society [4]. The ability to generate and share deepfakes on social networking platforms poses a significant threat to reputation and public trust. In 2017, a Reddit user created the first deepfake film by overlaying celebrity faces over obscene footage. Many techniques for detecting deepfake videos have been developed since then. While some of these techniques use convolutional neural networks to detect visual aberrations inside individual frames, others use recurrent neural networks to discover temporal anomalies across the facial frames in films. Recently, detecting deepfake videos has become an increasingly challenging task due to the complex

architecture of video sequencing and framing. Surveys report that numerous researchers have proposed deep learning-based methods for detecting deepfake videos. Accurate detection is still very difficult to achieve, though. For this, a number of deep learning methods have been used, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs), long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), and convolutional neural networks (CNNs). These algorithms examine many facets of video frames and sequences in order to spot anomalies and discrepancies that could be signs of deepfakes. In order to improve the identification of deepfake films, several authors have also presented the idea of transfer learning. This technique uses pre-trained models to increase the precision and effectiveness of detection techniques. In order to validate deep learning algorithms in deepfake detection, a number of benchmark datasets, including DFDC [5], Face Forensics [6], Face-Forensics++ [7], and DFD [8], have been used recently.

To evaluate its effect on generalizability, the usage of residual image input has also been investigated. The effectiveness of deepfake detection models is assessed both with and without the use of transfer learning. The best method for deepfake detection can be found by comparing and exploring several deep learning models. The best model for a given dataset can be chosen by researchers by examining the kinds of artificial artefacts that each model detects.

This paper proposes an efficient deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) for detecting deepfake videos. The proposed algorithm employs a dual constraint function within the convolutional neural network, enhancing its ability to identify deepfakes. These dual constraints allow the network to analyze temporal differences in video sequences, thereby determining whether a video is fake or real[9,10]. The performance of the proposed DCNN algorithm is compared with existing algorithms such as CNN, LSTM, and ResNet. By analyzing the temporal inconsistencies and manipulated artifacts in the video sequences, the proposed method aims to provide more accurate and reliable detection of deepfake videos than current state-of-the-art approaches.

Related Work

Because deepfake methods produce movies of excellent quality and are easily accessible to a wide range of people, they have become increasingly popular in recent times. FakeApp, Faceswap, DeepFaceLab, Faceswap Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), and DeepFake TensorFlow are a few of the most well-known deepfake face apps. These applications make use of GAN and autoencoder-decoder designs. In these systems, the decoder reconstructs the face images after the autoencoder has extracted hidden features from the face shots.

The authors of [1] examined pixel-based techniques for deepfake video detection. The detection approach finds lip-syncing, inpainting, style transfer, and super-resolution for the deepfake generation of video. The analysis of results has certain limitations in the temporal sequence difference of the video. In [2], the authors examined face-altering techniques in image deepfake detection. The process of detection as feature, measurement, or abstract-level integration for performance improvement.

In [3], authors proposed a CViT architecture for deepfake detection using CNN and Transformer. Emphasised diverse training data for deepfake detection in various settings. CNN and Vision Transformer components for deepfake detection.

In [4], the authors introduce a multimodal network for deepfake detection with spectral features. The study focuses on speed and accuracy in model evaluation. Multimodal system with NOLANet for video and audio processing.

In [5], the authors proceed with two-stage analysis with CNN and RNN for deepfake video detection. A two-stage algorithm was analysed with 600 videos, showing 94% accuracy in deepfake detection. CNN for frame-level feature extraction for temporal inconsistencies between frames.

In [6], the authors formulated deepfake detection as a spatial-temporal inconsistency learning process and proposed STIL blocks integrating spatial and temporal features in CNN. Spatial Inconsistency Module (SIM), Temporal Inconsistency Module (TIM), and Information Supplement Module (ISM).

In [7], authors proposed deepfake detection using deep neural networks (DNNs) for face images and videos. Study categories: Deepfake creation techniques are categorised into five major categories. Training deepfake models on deepfake datasets and testing with experiments. Monitoring visual consistency to estimate fake videos.

In [8], we proposed an algorithm for detecting fake face swapping technology with high accuracy. The proposed DenseNet169 model has a face-warping artefacts indicator for detection. Low-resolution faces

lead to a lack of skin details.

In [9], we investigated temporal variance in real and fake videos. Proposed latent pattern sensing model for deepfake video detection. Employed predictive learning mechanisms for self-supervised spatial and temporal features.

In [10], a study analysed the detection of forged videos using deepfake technology for face identification swaps. Comparison of an improved network with existing networks for detection accuracy.

In [11], the authors introduce the YIX architecture for deepfake detection using YOLO, InceptionResNetV2, and XGBoost. YOLO detector efficiency in object detection and face recognition systems. The XGBoost model produces competitive results in deepfake detection. YOLO face detector for face extraction from video frames; InceptionResNetV2 CNN for feature extraction from faces; XGBoost as a recognizer for distinguishing genuine and deepfake videos; The continuous development of deepfake techniques requires enhanced detection methods.

In [13], applying 3D input techniques for deepfake classification using the Celeb-DF dataset. Evaluating convolutional networks' performance for deepfake detection with temporal information. Spatiotemporal convolutional networks with random cropping and temporal jittering-trained convolutional networks on the Kinetics dataset for deepfake classification.

In [14], authors employed Detection of deepfake images using Mesonet CNN is proposed. The authors focus on deepfake creation, detection, experimental results, and concluding remarks.

In [15], authors proposed CNN, RNN, and autoencoder models using transfer learning. Transfer learning to autoencoders. A hybrid model of CNN and RNN for fake video detection.

In [16], it proposes hybrid recurrent models for deepfake video detection using temporal features. The proposed algorithm explores the hybridization of recurrent networks for temporal learning of video features. Hybrid recurrent deep learning models for deepfake video detections—GRU and GRU-LSTM models for improved accuracy.

Fig 1: Various deepfake detection techniques

To evaluate the performance, measure accuracy, precision, Recall, and F1-score. Most of the authors used the parameters is given below [23.24.25].

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \times 100$$

$$Sensitivity = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \times 100$$

$$Specificity = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \times 100$$

$$F1 - Score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \times 100$$

TP: True Positive

TN: True Negative

FP: False Positive

FN: False Negative

Study	Detection Method	Primary dataset	Technical Approach	Key Features
Ciftci and Demir, 2019	Neural network with biological signal analysis	Face Forensics, Face Forensics++, CelebDF, Custom Deep Fake Dataset	Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with biological signal Transformation	Uses biological signals as implicit descriptors of authenticity
Durall et al., 2019	Frequency domain analysis with classifier	Faces-HQ, CelebA, Face-Forensics++	Classical frequency domain analysis followed by basic classifier	Effective with few annotated samples, works in unsupervised scenarios
He et al., 2021	Re-synthesis with artifact detection	CelebA-HQ, FFHQ, LSUN	Neural network with image re-synthesis tasks	Focuses on reconstruction errors rather than low-level artifacts
Khan and Dang-Nguyen, 2024	Multiple deep learning models comparison	FakeAVCeleb, CelebDF-V2, DFDC, Face-Forensics++	CNNs and Transformer models	Compares supervised and self-supervised learning strategies
Korshunov and Marcel, 2022	Neural network with data augmentation	Google and Jigsaw, Face-Forensics++, DeeperForensics, Celeb-DF, DF-CMobio	Xception and EfficientNet models with augmentation	Focuses on improving generalization across datasets
Lin et al., 2022 Multiple detection methods benchmark	Multiple detection methods benchmark	UADFV, Celeb-DF, DF-1.0, DF-TIMIT, ForgeryNet	Various (knowledge-driven, data-driven, multi-stream),	Comprehensive evaluation of multiple detection approaches

Masi et al., 2020	Two-branch Re-current Network	Celeb-DF, DFDC preview set	network with frequency domain analysis	Combines RGB and frequency domain information
Rössler et al., 2019	Neural network approach	FaceForensics+ + Convolutional neural network(EfficientNet)		Large-scale dataset for training and evaluation
Shiohara and Yamasaki, 2022	Neural network with self-blended images	FF++, CDF, DFD, DFDC, DFDCP, FFIW	EfficientNet-b4 with novel training data generation	Uses self-blended images to improve generalization
Wang et al. 2023	Multiple detection methods comparison	Face Forensics++, Deepfake-TIMIT, Celeb-DF	Various (Two-stream, MesoNet, HeadPose, FWA, VA, Multi-task)	Focuses on Cross-library generalization

Table 1: Characteristics included in study

Study	In- Library Accuracy	Cross Library Accuracy	Implementation Challenges
Ciftci and Demir, 2019	96% 94.65% (Face Forensics++), 91.50% (CelebDF)	91.07% (Custom Deep Fakes Dataset)	Requires extraction and analysis of biological signals
Durall et al., 2019	(CelebA supervised), 96% (CelebA unsupervised)	100% low res, 91% (FaceForensics+ + low-res)	Potentially efficient due to classical approach
He et al., 2021	>85% to ~100% (CelebA-HQ)	Outperforms other methods on FFHQ	Involves complex re-synthesis process
Khan and Dang-Nguyen, 2024	Not mentioned	Not mentioned	Comparison of multiple architectures
Korshunov and	Not mentioned	Significant drop,	Requires data

Marcel, 2022		improved by augmentation and few-shot tuning	augmentation and few-shot tuning
Lin et al., 2022 Multiple detection methods benchmark	Area Under the Curve (AUC) 97.2% (Multiple-attention)	AUC: Multiple-attention (60.5%), Patch-Resnet-Layer1 (57.8%), Patch-Xception-Block2 (57.2%) Higher AUC on Celeb-DF compared to other methods	Inference time >5ms per frame for most methods
Masi et al., 2020	AUC 99% (FF++ medium compression), 91% (FF++ high compression)	Not mentioned	Combines RGB and frequency domain analysis
Rössler et al., 2019	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Large-scale dataset handling
Shiohara and Yamasaki, 2022	AUC 99.64% (FF++)	Outperforms state-of-the-art by 4.90% on DFDC, 11.78% on DFDCP	Requires generation of self-blended images
Wang et. Al. 2023	Not Mentioned	Significant degradation compared to in-library detection	Comparison of multiple architectures

Table 2: Performance Metrics

Study	Media Type	Effective against	Performance limitations
Ciftci and Demir, 2019	Videos	DeepFakes, Face2Face, FaceSwap, NeuralTextures	Lower accuracy on custom dataset
Durall et al., 2019	Images and Videos	Not mentioned	Lower accuracy on low-resolution videos
He et al., 2021	Images	ProGAN, StarGAN2, StyleGAN, StyleGAN2	Not mentioned
Khan and Dang-Nguyen, 2024	Videos	Not mentioned	Not mentioned

Korshunov and Marcel, 2022	Videos	Not mentioned	Significant drop in cross-dataset performance
Lin et al., 2022 Multiple detection methods benchmark	Videos	Autoencoder-based, GAN-based, mixed-	Poor performance on challenging ID test set
Masi et al., 2020	Videos	Not mentioned	Lower AUC for high compression videos
Rössler et al., 2019	Videos	DeepFakes, Face2Face, FaceSwap, NeuralTextures	Not Mentioned
Shiohara and Yamasaki, 2022	Videos	Not Mentioned	Varying performance across different datasets
Wang et. Al. 2023	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Significant degradation in cross-library scenarios

Table 3: Media type and performance limitations

Analysis of the literature reviewed:

Detection Methods:

Mostly used Detection method is neural networks second most shown on multiple models and very few uses frequency domain analysis, re-synthesis, and recurrent networks

Primary Datasets:

Most of the study is based on FaceForensics++

Celeb-DF was the second most common, used in 5 studies

DFDC was used in 4 studies

CelebA/CelebA-HQ and DeepfakeTIMIT were each used in 2 studies

15 other datasets were used in 1 study each

Technical Approaches:

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were the most common approach, used in 3 studies

EfficientNet models and various approaches were each used in 2 studies

5 other approaches (frequency domain, neural network, two-stream, Xception, and transformer) were each used in 1 study

Each of the studies we examined used a unique combination of detection method, dataset, and technical approach.

Research Gap

After the review of above literature following gap is identified for the new research
As per the review carried out it is found that many researchers used a CNN and another deep learning-based strategy to identify deepfake images, while others used feature-based techniques. To detect the deepfake images, few of them used machine learning classifiers. However very few of them work on detecting deep fake videos.

It is identified that the maximum researcher has worked on face swapped technique to detect the deepfake. Very few of them worked on the entire face synthesis approach for detecting the deep fake.

Researchers presented their work on specific datasets for Deepfake video detection hence Deepfake detection techniques lack generalization.

As AI powered Deepfake video generation techniques are getting more powerful Deepfake detection is more challenging now a days.

Conclusion

This study reviews 34 state-of-the-art research works on Deepfake detection published between 2019 and 2024. It outlines fundamental approaches and evaluates the performance of various detection models. The review highlights that deep learning techniques—particularly convolutional neural networks—are the most commonly adopted methods. Among the datasets used, FaceForensics++ appears most frequently across the surveyed studies. Detection accuracy remains the predominant performance metric for evaluating model effectiveness.

Despite the notable advancements in multimedia technologies and the growing availability of Deepfake generation tools, identifying manipulated content continues to pose significant challenges. This systematic literature review aims to serve as a comprehensive reference for researchers and practitioners, supporting the development of more robust, reliable, and future-ready Deepfake detection techniques and countermeasures.

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